

Shakespeare, F. Schiller, H. Heine, J.B.Molyer. From the first years the Azerbaijani theater, was an adherent of democratic and enlightening ideas. In addition to comedies MF. Akhundzade, the following plays were staged on the stage: "Woe to Fahreddin", "They ran away from the rain and fell under the downpour" by N. Vezirov, "The Ruined Nest", "The Unfortunate Youth", "Agha Muhammad Shah Gajar" A. Hagverdiyev, "Nadir Shah "And" Ignorance "by N. Narimanov, feudal traditions, a torturous regime, ignorance, despot of the capitalist system were shown in all these plays. In 1906 the company of "Muslim Dramatic Artists" was established. This company was led by the famous theater actor J. Zeynalov. Despite numerous persecutions and material losses, this company continued its activities and even enriched its personal repertoire. In 1908, with the charitable society "Nijat", a single dramatic company was formed, uniting such professional actors as G. Arablinsky, S. Rukhulla, A. Veli. The troupe had its own room, wardrobe, props. In addition, the troupe gave performances in the Tagiyev Theater and in the working areas. Significant events in the history of the Azerbaijani theatre were the performances of Agha Muhammad Shah Qajar by A. Akhverdiyev, "Blacksmith Giave," SamiSami, "Robbers"; "DeadMen" J. Mammadguluzade, in which the famous actor and director G. Arablinsky became famous, whose art was imbued with revolutionary and romantic pathos.

In 1910, a new cultural and educational society was established under the name "Safa" and with it a theatre department. The drama troupe of the Safa society was significantly weaker than the Nijat troupe. However, the actors of "Nijata" gradually began to move to "Safa". Active participation in the work of this society was accepted by D. Bunyatzade, the poet Samed Mansur, the actors G. Zeynalov, A. M. Sharifzade, from time to time the actors from the "Nijat" were invited to the performances of this performance - G.Arablinsky, M.Aliyev, S.Ruhulla, G.Sarabsky and others. The troupe of the Safa society, along with the organization of the performances, was also engaged in cultural and educational work related to the life of the theatre.

January 12 (according to the new style - January 25) in 1908 the foundation of the Azerbaijan professional music theatre was laid: on this day the performance of the first national opera was shown - the works of U. Hajibeyov "Leili and Majnun". In the first years of the musical theatre, his repertoire was enriched by the works of U. Hajibeyov, written 1908-1913 – operas «Leili and Mejnun», «Sheikh Sanan», «Rustam and Zohrab», «Shah Abbas and Khurshid Banu», «Esli and Kerem", musical comedies "Husband and wife", "Not that, this one", "Arshin Mal Alan".

In subsequent years, the repertoire of the Azerbaijan Musical Theater was enriched by the works of Z. Hajibeyov (opera "Ashig Garib", musical comedies "At fifty years old - young," "Married bachelor"), M.J. Amirov (opera "Seifalmulk"), etc. However despite the availability of its own repertoire, the music theatre felt a need for professional performers. In musical performances, along with such opera singers as G. Sarabsky, M. Mamedov (Bulbul), G. Hajibababekov, G. Teregulov, M. Bagirov, A. Agdamsky, mostly dramatic actors - G.Arablinsky (as a director) , A.Huseynzade, G.Abbasov, A. J.Olensky, R.Darabli, A.Anaply, etc. There was no clear division between musical and drama theatres, both dramatic and musical works were included in the repertoire of their troupes (in the 1910s most of their repertoires were musical performances).

In 1916, a play was staged for the comedy of J. Mamedgulizade "Oluler" ("Dead Men"). This performance was a testament to the ideological maturity of the Azerbaijani theatre. The play Dead Men, which sounded like a guilty verdict against the world of lies and oppression, religious fanaticism, was a huge success.

In 1917, the Union of Muslim Artists was established in Baku, the chairman of which was A.Sharifzadeh. This Union, having gathered around itself all theatrical units, organized the performances on the basis of comradesly relations.

References:

1. Timuchin Efendiyev. Methods in the Azerbaijan dramaturgy.
2. Narmina Agayeva. Azerbaijan theatrical criticism and the problems of the development of theatrical studies.
3. Iskandarov A.R. Belief in the future of our cinematography, Literature and Art.
4. Allahverdiyev M.G. Innovation and modern theatrical traditions.
5. Allahverdiyev M.G. The current state of the Azerbaijani theater, 1984.

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**СВОБОДА ЛИЧНОСТИ КАК КРИТЕРИЙ ОБЩЕСТВЕННОГО ПРОГРЕССА
(В ОЦЕНКЕ РУССКОГО НЕОНАРОДНИЧЕСТВА ПЕРВОЙ ЧЕТВЕРТИ XX ВЕКА)**

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**A FREEDOM OF THE INDIVIDUAL AS THE CRITERION OF SOCIAL PROGRESS
(in the assessment of Russian neo-populism the first quarter of the XXth century)**

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Аннотация. В статье анализируется отношение российских неонароднических партий — социалистов-революционеров и народных социалистов — к проблеме прав и свобод личности, которую они считали полноправным субъектом социальных взаимодействий и основой для построения социалистического общества. Показано, насколько значительное место уделяли в своих программных и тактических установках деятели этих партий принципам демократии, гуманизма и добра, и как в своей политической практике они совмещали страсть общественной борьбы и строгие нравственные императивы. Основные методы исследования: анализ, синтез, биографический метод, аналогия, сравнение.

Abstract. The article analyzes the attitude of Russian neo-populist parties — socialists-revolutionaries and people's socialists — to the problem of rights and freedoms of the individual, which they considered a full subject of social interactions and the basis for building a socialist society. It is shown how much the leaders of these parties devoted to the principles of democracy, humanism and good in their program and tactical settings, and how they combined the passion of public struggle and strict moral imperatives in their political practice. Main research methods: analysis, synthesis, biographical method, analogy, comparison.

Ключевые слова: свобода личности, политические партии, демократический социализм, либерализм, социалисты-революционеры, народные социалисты, этика в политике.

Keywords: individual freedom, political parties, democratic socialism, liberalism, socialists-revolutionaries, people's socialists, ethics in politics.

Свобода человеческой личности, ее всестороннее развитие — факторы, необходимые для роста уровня народного правосознания и, следовательно, для общественного прогресса. Поэтому в идейных построениях ведущих политических партий России с начала XX в. пункт о проблеме личности, реализации ее прав и свобод, хотя в различной форме и степени, но обязательно присутствовал. Такой «микросоциологический» подход в масштабах